

COMPARISON OF RISC AND CISC ARCHITECTURES – INSTRUCTION SET DESIGN DIFFERENCE

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Abstract—this paper has the comparison of two core processor architectures that is RISC and CISC focusing on their instruction set design, performance and hardware complexity. The paper further helps in exploring how architecture evolved, its strength and limitations also how the modern systems blend them both for a better approach. The study highlights how Artificial Intelligence tools can also optimize code translation between RISC and CISC, which improves efficiency across platforms.

Index Terms— RISC architecture, CISC architecture, instruction set design, processor performance, AI driven-code translation

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the field of computer science, the computer's architecture and the performance of its processor play a vital role in determining its efficiency, performance, capability, and overall market value. Processor architecture directly influences power efficiency, execution speed, and hardware complexity. Among the variety of various architectures, two of the major designs philosophies have been known famously from a decade: Reduced Instructions Set Computing (RISC) and Complex Instructions Set Computing (CISC). These both architectures differ primarily in their working by factor of complexity of their instruction sets and how they manage the tasks within the central processing unit (CPU).

RISC architecture focuses on keeping the instruction set smaller and simpler to enable a fast and effective execution of instruction per clock cycle, which improves the processing speed and reduces design complexity whereas a CISC architecture makes the instruction set more complex and larger which enables each instruction to be executed at multiple low levels, this architecture design minimizes the number of instructions per program but increases the hardware complexity.

The comparison between the two architectures remains a central topic in computer science, as both architectures present unique pros and cons. RISC focuses on providing higher performance and easy compiler optimization and CISC provides compact code and compatibility with older systems, understanding these properties and differences is an essential step for analysis of modern processors which sometimes combine RISC and CISC to build a hybrid model.

This paper presents the comparative analysis of RISC and CISC architectures based on the instruction complexity, hardware implementation, and memory and speed organization.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The evolution of instruction set design from complex to modern and RISC architectures, When IBM's system/360 came into existence in 1964, it marked the beginning of the modern computer architecture that introduced the distinction between two factors: computer architecture and hardware implementation [1] Before this invention the architectural decisions were done on the basis of cost of the hardware design and performance of that system. The System/360 introduced a key concept 'Microprogramming' that became the foundation for building processors that would be able to support large data instruction set efficiently. [1] [2] As semiconductor memory grew large in capacity during the 1970s, the computing community began commanding for an instruction set rich enough that will be able to reduce program size and improve speed of execution by using less amount of memory. But with the increment of more complex instruction set, controlling the hardware became a difficult task and would contribute to reducing the anticipated performance cons. These challenges later became the driving factor for the development of RISC architectures [2]. The development of RISC in early 1980's by researchers from IBM, Stanford and Berkeley helped in proving the fact that processor's with less and simpler instructions could actually run faster because of execution of each instruction in a single clock cycle. On the other hand, CISC architectures like Intel's x86 series were designed to perform more complex instruction sets in few to minimum steps which not only helped programs smaller but also allowed for old software to keep working on new computers. But as technology advanced, even the CISC processors started to include the RISC like features internally which means breaking down the complex instructions into smaller parts which will be faster, this shows how both approaches have influenced each other over time and have their own strengths [3], [4]. The comparison between RISC and CISC architectures enables us to understand the backend of the hardware design because they both have fundamentally different designs that shaped modern computing. The RISC works with simplicity, efficiency and executes most

instructions per clock cycle, which simplifies instruction execution and maintain compatibility. On the other hand, CISC emphasizes on complex instructions that perform multiple tasks in fewer lines of codes. In modern processors, both concepts have merged to some extent, and understanding their differences helps in evaluating how each architecture contributes to hardware complexity and software optimization [3], [4]. Recent research also explores how modern AI techniques can help bridge the gap between CISC and RISC instruction sets. For example, Heakl *et al.* [5] proposed a language-model-guided transpiler that converts x86 (CISC) assembly into ARM (RISC) assembly with up to 1.73× performance improvement over traditional virtualization methods such as Rosetta 2.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research paper uses a combination of inquiry and investigations to perceive the process by which computers shift from CISC architecture to RISC architecture. At the start we reviewed and analyzed the concept of the two architectures, for example the process by which their commands work and how the data is handled. The target was to perceive how the basic command design and data handling techniques of RISC architecture help to run the program faster and easier and more efficiently than the complex commands of CISC systems.

In the following step, we examined the efficiency studies on RISC and CISC processors including IBM POWER and Intel Woodcrest. We analyzed both systems by checking how they utilize clock cycle, the time they take to run, and how smoothly they processed instructions. Their results help us to grasp how much improved the CISC processors are and get closer in performance to RISC architecture because of enhanced design and command handling.

At last, a language model that used to transform (or “convert”) CISC assembly code into RISC assembly code. A huge collection of x86 and ARM assembly programs was used to train this model, enabling it to identify the pattern between the two types. By using software tools, the model’s results to verify the converted code were accurate and worked properly. This step illustrates that artificial intelligence helps to improve the code performance and efficiency on different types of computers.

IV. RESULTS

The result of the research shows how that RISC and CISC architectures, each one of them bring distinct strengths, but with modern computing increasingly benefits from hybrid approach that merge both RISC with simpler and smaller instruction set, gets faster execution and efficiency by completing most instruction in a single clock cycle on the other hand CISC with its larger and more complex instruction set, which reduces program size and maintains backward compatibility though at the cost of higher hardware complexity. Evaluations of performance of

processors like Intel Woodcrest (CISC) and IBM POWER (RISC) shows that design makes more improvement have reduced the performance differences with CISC processors executing internal characteristics similar to RISC. Additionally, AI driven code translators have effectively converted CISC assembly into RISC assembly and give the notable performance, seeing how effective AI has become in filling the gap between two. According to the research findings, modern processor are more efficient when they combine the best of two different architectures rather than depending only on one. Future advancement will be made by fusing hardware innovation with clever software solutions to optimize compatibility, speed and efficiency.

V. DISCUSSION

On the basis of the above research and the analysis of RISC and CISC architectures, this discussion highlights the main results and their relation to earlier studies.

When we look at both RISC and CISC architectures, we can see that CPU designs are continuously evolving over time, becoming faster, more efficient, capable of handling complex tasks, and more adaptable to new technologies. RISC has a simpler instruction set that makes program execution faster, whereas CISC architectures use more complex instructions that make programs shorter but increase hardware complexity and power usage.

The performance of computer systems and their choices directly impact on overall efficiency.

If we compare the working of these processors, RISC architectures executes the instructions more faster because they are designed for simpler operations, whereas CISC processors handle more complex operations. Over time, both architectures have combined their strengths. For example, CISC processors maintain backward compatibility and use improved compiler optimization, which could narrow the performance gap between RISC and CISC leading toward hybrid designs.

Through various experiments, it has been proven that the use of artificial intelligence can reduce the difference between RISC and CISC architectures and their performances. AI-driven code translators can be taken as an example as they are used for converting CISC code into RISC-based code making the programs efficient and capable to run on various types of hardware. This elaborates that computing has entered a new phase that focuses on how smart software can be instead of only focusing on hardware. In modern systems, intelligent programs are being implemented that are able to learn, adapt, and produce better outcomes.

The above research concludes that today’s computers are more efficient because they does not use RISC or CISC alone, but integrate the best features of both. The main point is that if we merge the strengths of RISC and CISC, the performance of modern processors will become more efficient. However, if this research continues, it could provide a better understanding by testing real-world

applications, leading to more efficient and compatible system performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study went through how the architectures of RISC and CISC each of them bring different unique strengths to design of processor. Faster execution and greater efficiency is a trait which is delivered by RISC systems and CISC systems, on the other hand, reduce program size and help the older software to keep working but with more hardware power. Then we compared the processors like IBM POWER (RISC) and Intel Woodcrest (CISC), in which we saw that the recent and newer designs have made CISC work more like RISC which is closing the gap between two. We also found out that AI tools can translate the CISC code into RISC code which helps the programs run better across different systems. In the end, we conclude that today's processor work best when both of the architecture's strength mix together.

VII. FUTURE WORK

While the study shows the comparison and the benefits of combining RISC and CISC architectures, future research can explore many other key areas. First area can be how AI-based code translators can be made faster and more efficient across different platforms. It would also be useful to focus on how to make AI tools better at translating code between the two systems, for a faster and smoother performance, it will also be useful to explore how machine learning can help predict which instructions are needed, so processors can work smarter and smoother performance. Most importantly, teamwork between hardware experts and software developers will help in making the systems that are faster, more compatible and those that save energy.

VIII. REFERENCES

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